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Research Guide

The Maharaja Sayajirao University of
Baroda (GJ)**Abstract:**

The paper enhances information and knowledge management, web technology and knowledge sharing, which may be applied in the field of library and information professional user's friendly developments in ICT. Mostly identify the opportunities provided through a networked computer. A more encompassing perspective will come about if Information and Communication Technology is studied in relation to the utilization for development and implement interactive user interfaces and applications using new web tools and services for collaborative information services and knowledge sharing the emerging technologies in the world.

Keywords: Computer Technology, World Wide Web, Networking Technology, Information Technology and ICT.

Introduction:

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become so much popular and is most widely used. It is the pronounced buzzword of the computer industry. It has helped people of all walks of life in one way or the other. ICT is the modern science of gathering, storing, manipulating, processing and communicating the desired types of information in a specific environment. 'Computer technology and 'Communication technology' are the two main supporting pillars of this technology and the impact of these two in the information storage and dissemination is vital. It is next to impossible to deny the importance of Information and Communication Technologies in the educational, cultural, agricultural, scientific and technical areas of the human involvement. Information needs are increasing day by day and today each one is intending to be information oriented.

☞ ICT for Automation:

‘Computer Technology’ is similar to one face of a coin (Information Technology). A tremendous revolution has taken place in the last decades. The networks make possible a wide range of communication services that include Electronic Mail, Facsimile Transmission, Bulletin – Board service, Teletext, Videotext, Voice Systems, Voice Message Systems, Teleconferencing, Audio conferencing, Audio graphics, and Videoconferencing.

All the above services make use of special equipments, computer based message systems and computer networks. The special equipments include: Fax Machine, EPBX, Automatic Telephone Dialler, Voice Recognition systems, Voice Synthesizers, Data Networks, Commercial Databases, Optical Disk Storage & Retrieval Systems, Telex Terminals, Communicating Word – Processors, Slow – Scan TV, High – Definition TVs, and so on.

☞ Meaning of ICT:

To understand Information and communication technology, we need to know about the terms, information, communication and technology. Information is data that has been processed to make it meaningful to its recipients, where data is unprocessed information. Communication is a means for transmitting information. Technology is a means of consciously transforming inputs into outputs. ICT is a means of passing the information from one to other, using some technology.

☞ Advantages of ICT:

- 1) It will help us to eliminate drudgery in our routines and introduce speed, flexibility and control in the slow moving, rigid, and repetitive procedures whether in our personal life or in the organizational setup.
- 2) They will have to access to, use and communicate information from a variety of sources. By applying their knowledge of ICT skilfully, they will find everything at their doorstep without any hassle.
- 3) The ICT is being portrayed, and validly so, as a major force for organizational, managerial, educational and research force.
- 4) By using ICT only can the managers, research scholars, teachers, librarians, heads of organizations, athletic trainers, industrialists, economists and others were able to improve their performance in their respective fields of interaction and add to their efficiency.
- 5) ICT will encourage and enhance the possibilities for collaborative research.
- 6) Perhaps the greatest beneficiary of ICT would be the individual and the society at large.

Disadvantages of ICT:

- 1) The ICT is impinging upon the natural development of man as thinking and acting machine. It is taking away the initiative human brain takes in thinking and creating ideas, since everything is now being controlled and done by computers.
- 2) Every one, without age, gender or status discrimination, has an authorized or unauthorized access to any and every nonsensical information and knowledge on any subject and aspect of life, which sometimes may be purely personal and private.
- 3) The problem of hackers – those abuse computers by illegal, unauthorized or “hacking” activities and the cyber terrorists are increasingly becoming more acute and no authority, whatsoever, is in a position to stem the tide of this kind of crime and overcome looming danger to human morality and ethics.
- 4) We know how terrorist activity through the length and breadth of the Globe is being carried out by unscrupulous criminals against the humanity.
- 5) The speed with which technology is overshadowing each and every aspect of life, and rendering man subservient to machine, the possibility of life losing humanistic quality and man entering the Brave New World much earlier than Aldous Huxley visualized, cannot be ruled out.

Librarians and the ICT:

In the changing perception of educational process worldwide librarians, are no longer considered as dispensers of knowledge but rather proactive facilitators who promote collaborative knowledge building and guide students to learn in a variety of environments, to navigate within and process a multitude of information sources, and to use these resources in solving variety of problems (of men especially students, materials, methods and management) and making decisions(about students and themselves, teaching – learning processes and procedures) on their own.

When the issue of integration of ICT into the educational system is looked into from a larger perspective, the factors that have been identified as problem areas in our country in the present situation include:

- 1) Accessibility and affordability
- 2) Integration of ICT in the curriculum
- 3) Shortage of trained manpower
- 4) Librarians fear of the technology and lack motivation
- 5) Closed mindset of the school and college administration and lack of appreciation for ICT in education
- 6) Budgetary constraints – most investment being in the area of hardware, rather than for improving skills, competencies and production of librarians.

- 7) Maintenance of ICT resources and lack of technical staff
- 8) Sustainability
- 9) Limited availability of educational software and courseware

Internet:

The Internet is the largest “network of networks” today, and the closest model we have for information in a superhighway.

Important Telecommunication Service on the Internet (Internet Protocols):

Following are the important telecommunication services on the Internet:

1) **E-Mail:**

Exchange electronic mail with millions of Internet users. Electronic mail has crossed all barriers of space and time as one can communicate at an amazing speed through computer network. It is a very economical way of transmitting messages expeditiously.

2) **TCP/IP (Transmission Control Protocol/ Internet Protocol):**

It is a collection of protocols or rules that govern the way data travel from one machine or system to another across networks.

3) **Usenet:**

Post messages on bulletin board systems formed by the thousands of special interest discussion groups.

4) **HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol):**

It is referred to as a protocol or set of rules which govern the transfer of hypertext between two or more computers.

5) **Internet Relay Chat:**

Hold real time conversations with Internet users around the world on hundreds of discussion channels.

6) **FTP (File Transfer Protocol):**

Download data files, programmes, reports, articles, magazines, books, pictures, sounds, and other types of files from thousands of sources to your computer system. This is a very powerful tool which enables users to transfer from “computer A” to “computer B”. Vice versa.

7) **WAIS (Wide Area Information Service):**

It is an Internet search tool that is based on the Z39.50 standard, which describes a protocol, or set of rules, computer – to – computer information retrieval.

8) **Telenet:**

Also known as remote login, this protocol, enables to log on and use thousands of Internet computer systems around the world.

9) Gopher:

It is a protocol designed to search, remove and display documents from remote sites on the Internet. Besides, document display and document retrieval, it is possible to initiate on – line connections with other systems via gopher.

10) IP Address:

Should a person wish to connect to another computer, transfer files to or from another computer, or send an e-mail message, such a person first needs to find out the location of the other computer or know its “address”.

11) Domain Name:

A domain identifies and locates computers connected to the Internet.

☞ World Wide Web:

The World Wide Web (also known as the Web or WWW) as a method for incorporating footnotes, figures, and cross references into online documents. The Web’s creators wanted to create a simple way to access any document that was stored on a network, without having to search through indexes or directories of files, and without having to manually copy documents from one computer to another before viewing them. To do this, they established a way to ‘link’ documents that were stored in different locations on a single computer, or on different computers on a network.

☞ Future of the ICT:

ICT has the capability to prepare a learner for a rapidly changing world scenario. They may use ICT as a tool to find, explore, analyze, exchange and present information as per their need. The capabilities of ICT may be used for library professionals in the following ways.

- 1) Providing a knowledge network to the learners
- 2) Enhancing library professionals
- 3) Broadening the availability of quality e- contents
- 4) Providing contents on demand
- 5) Professional development and recurrent training of librarians
- 6) Creating a virtual environment
- 7) Web – based teaching and learning
- 8) Videoconference
- 9) Mobile learning

☞ Conclusion:

Technology is now widely available to enable communication of information in addition to storage and retrieval of information. The World Wide Web (WWW) is the largest source of